

A Climate OSSE Capability for NASA Earth Sciences

Prepared for the NASA Office of Earth Science by

Stephen S. Leroy (Harvard University)

Bruce A. Wielicki (NASA Langley Research Center)

William D. Collins (Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory and
University of California, Berkeley)

Daniel R. Feldman (Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory)

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1. Background and rationale

In order to address priorities in Earth observation, NASA Earth Sciences requested the advice of the National Academies of Science on which observing systems should be continued and what new missions are needed. In response, the National Research Council assembled a panel to discuss these very issues and published the Continuity Study¹. The published study states that NASA Earth Sciences should make decisions on Earth observation missions according to five criteria: the *importance* of a well-defined and quantifiable scientific objective, the *utility* of the proposed measurements to address the scientific objective, the *quality* of the measurements as specified by the observing system's requirements, the *probability* of success of the mission, and the *affordability* of the mission. The importance of a mission's scientific objective is determined from a subjective consensus of the climate research community and can come in the form of recommendations from the NASA Earth Science Decadal Survey or designated review panels. The probability of success is rated according to the technological readiness of the mission's components by a team of engineers designated by NASA. The affordability of a mission is judged using NASA cost models in light of NASA's budget for Earth Sciences. The utility and the quality, though, can be quantified objectively using a Climate Observation System Simulation Experiment, or a "Climate OSSE."

A Climate OSSE (or "COSSE" hereafter), is similar to its namesake OSSE from Numerical Weather Prediction (NWP) in that it uses simulated observations to evaluate computationally how well a proposed observing system can achieve a well specified objective. In numerical weather prediction, the specified objective is improvement in near-term weather forecasts. In climate, however, the specified objective can be anything from improved multi-decadal predictions of sea level rise and extreme weather to more reliable multi-century predictions of temperature change. In a COSSE, the observations are relevant to far more than just the thermodynamics and dynamics of the atmosphere. Hence, while the core of an NWP OSSE is a data assimilation system that resolves especially the lower atmosphere, the core of a COSSE is a climate model that incorporates all processes thought to be relevant to climate. The climate model must encompass the physical, chemical, and biogeochemical states of the ocean, atmosphere, land surface, and sea and land ice. In an instance of a COSSE, the observations of a proposed observing system are independently simulated and fused with the climate model. The outcome is a reduction in uncertainty in the scientific objective, a priori to a posteriori. The degree of reduction in uncertainty is the objective quantification of the utility and quality of a proposed observing system. In an NWP OSSE, the method of fusing simulated data with an atmospheric model is data assimilation, which itself is a form of Bayesian inference. Objective mathematical formulations can even count the number of bits of information an observing system provides². In a COSSE, a Perturbed Physics Ensemble (PPE) of a climate model is used to fully quantify uncertainty in present-day climate. A control subset is extracted from the PPE that agree with current observing systems to within specified tolerances, and an experimental subset is also extracted from the PPE that satisfies these observational constraints and that also agree with the simulated new observations to within a pre-selected margin of error. The members

¹ *Continuity of NASA Earth Observations from Space: A Value Framework*, National Research Council, National Academies Press, 112pp, 2016.

² C. Cardinali, *Q. J. Royal Meteor. Soc.*, **135**, 239–250, 2009.

of the experimental subset will produce a narrower distribution of the well-specified scientific objective than those of the control subset, and the degree to which the distribution is narrowed is the quantified and objective evaluation of the utility and quality of the proposed observing system.

Full uncertainty quantification of climate is to be obtained through PPEs to the extent that uncertainty is understood. Quantification of the uncertain physics of the climate system needs to be accomplished in order to credibly evaluate the utility of measurements. Here we understand that the uncertain “physics” of the climate are all those processes in a model of the climate that are unresolved by the model grid and integration time step and thus must be parameterized if their influence is to be accounted for. It includes not just atmospheric and oceanic processes but chemical, biological, geophysical, and ice morphological processes as well. Uncertainty quantification, though, is a difficult exercise; hence, the National Research Council produced a document³ for its best practices. A COSSE for the sake of the Office of Earth Science need not account for structural uncertainty inasmuch as the goal of a COSSE is a rating of utility and quality of proposed observation system in the light of the known behaviors and uncertainties in climate rather than the unknown. In fact, all climate studies that have undertaken some form of Bayesian uncertainty quantification have been a type of COSSE, and in that sense the idea of a COSSE is not a new one.

Most importantly, it has been repeated frequently that the U.S. does not have a coordinated climate observing system (Trenberth et al. 2013). In the Anthropocene, in which humans are exerting a geologically recognizable forcing on the Earth system, the need for a climate observing system should be transparently obvious. Many measurements are being made, but to date no unified policy of observing changes in the climate system has been implemented. A credible climate observing system should provide data that is global, rich in information content, accurate, and reproducible⁴. The climate observing system should obtain global coverage and data that is rich in information in order that future generations can examine change in geophysical variables that the present generation does not yet appreciate. The climate observing system should be accurate and reproducible in order to confront models, enable deeper scientific understanding of the Earth’s climate, and prove definitively that observed changes are real and not instrumental artifacts. The role of a COSSE applied to the design of a climate observing system is to maximize the information content desired for testing climate models according to their long-term predictive capability and to provide measurement requirements that assure that those observations can be useful in a reasonable time frame.

While this white paper focuses on the development of COSSEs, many of the characteristics, approaches, and challenges also apply to other types of OSSEs that are relevant to NASA science goals.

2. What is a COSSE?

A climate OSSE or COSSE is a statistical computation based upon arbitrarily complex models of the climate that objectively evaluates mission requirements,

³ *Assessing the Reliability of Complex Models: Mathematical and Statistical Foundations of Verification, Validation, and Uncertainty Quantification*, National Research Council, National Academies Press, 131pp, 2012.

⁴ R. Goody et al., *Bull. Amer. Meteor. Soc.*, **83**, 873–878, 2002.

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instrument requirements, and measurement requirements for proposed observing systems and quantifies the value each one adds to testing well-defined hypotheses or to improving climate prediction.

A COSSE is a computation that determines whether or not a proposed set of measurements can achieve a well-defined scientific objective in light of its stated instrumentation, sampling pattern, and measurement uncertainty characteristics. In the case of a proposed observing system that has improved prediction skill as its scientific objective, the quantified scientific objective is long-term prediction or another inferred quantity of the climate, in which the proposed measurements are useful for reducing uncertainty in the quantified scientific objective. In the case of testing scientific hypotheses, the COSSE evaluates the ability of the proposed observing system to distinguish between competing hypotheses. Also, a COSSE can be used to specify observing system—mission requirements, science requirements, instrument requirements, mission duration—when in the process of designing a mission.

It is essential that every mission have a specific, quantifiable, well-defined scientific objective¹. Examples of such scientific objectives are

- Determine the rate of acceleration of sea level rise to 1 mm/yr/decade.
- Determine global annual aerosol forcing with an uncertainty of 0.2 Wm^{-2} .
- Reduce uncertainty in equilibrium climate sensitivity (ECS) by a factor of 2 relative to the IPCC AR5.
- Reduce the uncertainty in domestic hurricane damage per decade by a factor of 2 relative to the IPCC AR5 report for the full range of IPCC emission scenarios.
- Reduce the uncertainty in the change of drought and flood extremes for the IPCC emissions scenarios by a factor of 2.

Each scientific objective is a single quantifiable scalar.

A COSSE must connect a forward model for observations to output variables of the core model to evaluate this scalar for each member of a PPE. For example, an observing system that measures radiance would require that a radiance forward model be built into the core model to simulate radiance based on temperature, water vapor, clouds, aerosol, other absorbing and reflecting species. An active sensor such as a cloud radar would require a model that simulates radar reflectivity based on suspended and precipitating water and ice meteors and sharp gradients in millimeter wave refractivity. Techniques would also be introduced for outputting the simulated measurements from these forward models along the time-evolving ground tracks or fields of view of the hypothetical satellites carrying the proposed instruments.

COSSEs for improving prediction skill and for scientific hypothesis testing are discussed below, followed by a discussion of establishing observing system requirements with a COSSE. An overview of the statistical theory for a COSSE framework is given in Appendix A, §10.

2.1. Improving prediction skill

NASA observations are often designed to improve the prediction of weather, air quality, or climate change. NASA addresses the improvement of prediction with observing systems as process studies or through long-term monitoring. A process study consists of high spatial-temporal resolution observations that are restricted in time with the intent to study process physics that underlie the climate system. Examples of observations for process studies are field experiments or A-train data for studying clouds. Long-term monitoring entails observing

commitments that last greater than a decade with assured accuracy and reproducibility that can be used to constrain models according to their predictive capability. Even after parameterized model physics is designed in accordance with the findings of process study missions, the models that result must still be tested according to their predictive capability by climate monitoring.

The reduction in uncertainty in a well-defined quantified scientific objective can be determined without simulating observations independently. It is only necessary to evaluate the correlation coefficient ρ between simulated observations and scientific objective across all the members of a PPE of a climate model. If the correlation between simulated observations and scientific objective is high (positive or negative), then the observing system will greatly reduce uncertainty in the scientific outcome and will do so by a factor $(1 - \rho^2)^{1/2}$. If the observing system does not address a major contributor to uncertainty in the scientific objective, the correlation coefficient will be small and the observing system should be deemed irrelevant. A large correlation coefficient means high *utility*; a small correlation coefficients means low *utility*.

For both process study and long-term monitoring, a COSSE simulates observations using models at the time and space scale appropriate for the proposed observation. Different versions of models would likely be used for each case. The PPE that is needed for every instance of a COSSE must consist of hundreds to thousands of members, or independent model runs; thus, models must be degraded in spatial-temporal resolution or spatial coverage in some way in order to permit large numbers of model runs. Observing systems intended for the study of small-scale or regional processes necessitate high spatial resolution models that are limited in spatial extent. Models such as cloud resolving models (CRM) and large eddy simulation (LES) models are limited in time and domain but have very high spatial resolution (~ 10 m for a large eddy simulator, ~ 1 km for a cloud-resolving model) and are appropriate to study process-oriented observing systems. Observing systems intended for global climate monitoring necessitate global coverage and so must sacrifice extremely high spatial resolution in the core model of its PPE. Earth System models, with spatial resolution of ~ 100 km and simulation times of centuries, are appropriate climate monitoring observing systems. The difference between high-resolution and low-resolution climate models is narrowing, however. New computers are capable of running LES over ~ 100 -km domains, and if major computers are used (e.g., the large GPU machine at Oak Ridge National Laboratory) the domain could reach 1000 km in scale with a spatial resolution of 50 meters. Also, multi-scale models are being developed that can run high resolution models embedded within limited domains of global models. Some climate groups have even run CRM-scale global models for limited time periods.

2.2. Scientific hypothesis testing

NASA observations are often designed to answer scientific questions about the Earth system. Such questions are most rigorous when posed as a hypothesis test. At least two hypotheses A and B are posed. A COSSE is implemented in this problem by developing a PPE for each of the two hypotheses, one that fundamentally incorporates the processes of hypothesis A into the model, and the other incorporates the processes that define hypothesis B into the model. The first PPE predicts a distribution of observations $O(A)$, and the second predicts a distribution of observations $O(B)$. If NASA Earth Sciences were to produce an observing system that obtains data D , and if D is clearly more consistent with $O(A)$ than it is with $O(B)$, then hypothesis A is objectively preferable to theory B in light of the data. The role of the COSSE in scientific hypothesis testing is determining whether distributions of simulated observations $O(A)$ and $O(B)$ are discernably different. In scientific hypothesis testing, a COSSE determines the *utility* of an

observing system according to the separability of the distributions $O(A)$ and $O(B)$ in the absence of measurement error. Testable hypotheses can be applied to competing climate models, cloud models, chemistry models, ocean models, ice sheet models, carbon cycle models, and ecosystem models.

2.3. Observing system duration

For a class of observing system that requires climate monitoring to improve predictive skill or to perform hypothesis testing, the duration of the observing system is of prime importance. The existence of naturally occurring internal variability in the climate system has the effect of reducing the correlation coefficient for observing systems intended to improve predictive skill and broadening the distributions of $O(A)$ and $O(B)$ for hypothesis testing. Lengthening the duration of an observing system has the effect of averaging out the fluctuations of natural variability and increasing the correlation coefficient and tightening the distributions $O(A)$ and $O(B)$. The longer the time-series of data for climate monitoring, the better the *utility* of the observing system. Climate monitoring systems require that the major modes of natural variability be averaged over many of their cycles. The largest in the climate system is the El Niño-Southern Oscillation with a quasi-periodicity of ~ 5 years. Thus, climate monitoring requires a baseline of multiple decades. This cannot be accomplished with a single instance of a satellite mission. Either a dedicated program of a series of satellites is required or a series of intermittent climate benchmarks is needed over the coming decades. The former degrades the long-term *affordability* because of the long-term commitment required, and the latter degrades the *utility* of an observing system because of periodic gaps in the temporal sampling. A COSSE can be used to quantify how the *utility* of a proposed observing system for climate monitoring is impacted by its duration and intermittency of satellite missions by changing each in the simulations of observations.

2.4. Accuracy and precision requirements

Inaccuracy and imprecision in measurements degrades the ability of an observing system to improve predictive skill or distinguish between competing hypotheses. A COSSE reveals the degree to which specified levels of inaccuracy and imprecision of measurements can impact predictive skill, which is done by adding noise to the simulated observations produced by the members of the PPE of the COSSE. For imprecision, the noise is white and hence independent from one measurement to the next. For inaccuracy, the noise is strongly correlated in some way, whether it's a systematic offset for each proposed instrument or a slow drift in calibration. The result of inaccuracy and imprecision is always a degradation of the correlation coefficient between simulated observation and scientific objective. The result is a decreased ability to improve predictive skill and a reduced *quality* of measurements. Likewise, a COSSE reveals the degree to which hypothesis testing is degraded by inaccuracy and imprecision of measurements. Both have the effect of adding spread to the clusters of observations $O(A)$ and $O(B)$, and too much additional spread would cause their distributions to overlap. Once there is too much overlap, a proposed set of observations can no longer distinguish between scientific hypotheses and the *quality* of the measurements is reduced.

Measurement accuracy is of particular importance to observing systems dedicated to climate monitoring. Many have advocated for assured mission overlap to develop climate data records from inter-mission comparison and bias correction, but instrument artifacts have shown repeatedly that overlap and bias correction is often insufficient for climate monitoring purposes. Empirically demonstrable measurement accuracy using sound metrological methods and mission

reproducibility are essential. Accuracy requirements on climate monitoring systems can be established by a COSSE through simulations of bias in a series of instances of satellite missions added to simulations of measurements. A lower bound on required accuracy is tied to the duration of individual satellite missions and the amplitude and periodicity of natural variability⁵. An upper bound should be tied to degradation of the *quality* of observing systems. Inaccuracy in climate monitoring is tolerable until it becomes large enough that it can no longer be mined to improve climate prediction or distinguish between scientific hypotheses. It is possible to tighten the requirements on accuracy for a climate monitoring system if its utility is already judged to be strong, but more stringent requirements on measurement accuracy frequently entail reduction of the *affordability* of an observing system.

2.5. Sampling requirement studies

The cost of an observing system scales nonlinearly with the space and time sampling required. It is also strongly affected by the diurnal sampling and size of the footprint. The effects of sampling patterns on the quality of an observing system can be evaluated by subsetting the output simulated observations of the proposed observing system according to different proposed sampling patterns. Because observing systems intended for process studies target processes that occur on small scales, they require dense sampling in space and small footprints but not necessarily global coverage. Such sampling requirements are usually met by proposed satellite missions designed to fly in low-Earth orbits. If the sampling is not dense enough to resolve the intended small-scale processes, the outcome of the COSSE will be that the observing system's *quality* will be penalized: what could have been useful observations won't be as useful as they could have been. Other satellite-based observing systems intended for process studies are appropriately placed in geostationary orbits in order to obtain high temporal resolution, thereby recording the history of specific short-duration climate phenomena. A COSSE can be used to specify greater spatial resolution or temporal resolution and reduced footprint size to gain improved *quality*, yet such improvements entail greater expense, thus decreasing an observing system's *affordability*.

Whereas observing systems for process studies are limited in duration, observing systems for climate monitoring require decades of observations to overcome the noise of naturally occurring internal variability in the climate system such as the El Niño/Southern Oscillation, the quasi-biennial oscillation, and the Pacific Decadal Oscillation. A climate monitoring observing system is composed of a series of satellites that obtain unbiased, highly accurate measurements, thereby obviating the need for and dependence on mission overlap. Inappropriate sampling patterns for climate monitoring can incur bias by inadequate sampling of the diurnal cycle for observables with large diurnal cycles or by inadequate sampling of the geometry of outgoing radiation for radiance fields with complicated directional radiance structure. Bias is the most undesirable outcome for a climate monitoring system. Commonly, satellite-based atmospheric observing systems are tied to a specific local time in order to eliminate variability due to the diurnal cycle. [A heritage of sun-synchronous orbits derives from the prerogatives of numerical weather prediction, which, for the sake of operational data assimilation, demands that all data be gathered a set times of day every day.] Climate monitoring, though, often requires the opposite: complete coverage of the diurnal cycle should be obtained. Coverage of the diurnal cycle can be obtained either by placing satellites in rapidly precessing orbits or by placing many satellites in

⁵ Wielicki et al., *Bull. Amer. Meteor. Soc.*, **94**, 1519–1539, 2013.

complementary orbits. A COSSE will automatically quantify the deleterious effects of diurnal cycle bias on the observing system's *quality* if the simulated data of each member of the PPE is subset according to the proposed sampling pattern for a proposed observing system.

2.6. Compare multiple observing system options

NASA is often confronted with more than one observing system that addresses the same scientific objective. A COSSE is ideally suited to evaluating the ability of each to reduce uncertainty in the scientific objective or test its capability of distinguishing between scientific hypotheses. This is done by specifying a forward model for the measurements proposed for each observing system, adding measurement error according to the requirements of each, and subsampling according to the sampling pattern specified by each. The one that yields the greatest correlation coefficient between observation and scientific objective, or the one that produced the most distinct distributions $O(A)$ and $O(B)$ for scientific hypothesis testing is the most preferable in considering *utility* and *quality*.

3. Five key characteristics of a COSSE

A COSSE is a rigorous tool to evaluate the requirement of an observing system and to evaluate the amount of information it offers toward a well-defined scientific objective. There are five characteristics of a COSSE because of (1) the much broader range of problems it must address than does an NWP OSSE, (2) the range of complexity of climate models and the systems they account for, and (3) the different problems confronted at various stages of development of an Earth Science mission. The five characteristics are empiricism vs. inference, weak model vs. strong model, degree of sophistication, complementarity vs. verification, process study vs. model test. The type of COSSE to be formulated can differ depending on the characteristics of the specific objective. The characteristics listed below are not necessarily wholly independent.

3.1. Empiricism vs. inference

In some COSSEs, the observables of an observing system directly lead to the scientific objective whereas in other COSSEs the relationship between observable and scientific objective is far less direct. The former is considered “empiricism” because the process of reaching the scientific objective depends almost entirely on the measurements alone. The latter is considered “inferential” because it is necessary to form relationships between observable and scientific objective using a model. A COSSE can be applied in either case.

A COSSE for an empirical mission is needed to formulate requirements for sampling, accuracy and precision requirements. It will always be the case that an observing system under-samples the climate system. Hence, the error incurred by a sampling pattern must be evaluated by “flying a satellite through a model”. Error estimates can be computed for several different sampling patterns, and those that minimize the sampling error are deemed preferable. In some cases, it may be possible to perform a COSSE for the sake of analyzing sampling error with data rather than a model. Such a situation arises when an observing system has previously obtained data on the same geophysical variable of interest as the proposed observing system but with greater sampling density. Examples of empirical missions are those with the objective of measuring long-term climate change in a geophysical variable.

A COSSE for an inference mission requires that the core climate model includes the physics necessary to address the scientific objective of the observing system. The role of the data

to be obtained is to reduce some of the uncertainty in the physics that is responsible for uncertainty in the scientific objective. The climate model to be used in this COSSE must be executed many times, varying the physics within expert uncertainty bounds, in an exercise in Bayesian uncertainty quantification². Conditioning the uncertainty in the scientific objective on data that is brought to bear will always reduce uncertainty in the scientific objective. Different observables, though, will reduce the uncertainty in the scientific objective by different degrees. The one that reduces the uncertainty in the scientific objective the most is the preferred observable and is deemed to have higher *utility*. Natural variability in the observable serves to obscure the relationship between observation and a scientific objective. Longer missions will reduce the effect of natural variability. Also, measurement error and sampling error also obscure the relationship between observation and scientific objective. The COSSE can be used to determine what levels of measurement error are tolerable.

3.2. Strong model vs. weak model

A COSSE almost always requires a model, most often a climate model. Modeling that is relevant to the scientific objective may not be respected in the research community because few people trust it to be able to capture well-known phenomena in the climate system that the research community expects it to capture. For example, models that incorporate the physics of ice rheology and melting processes at small and large scales necessary to predicting sea level rise are only beginning to be developed and are not yet trusted for a full accounting for uncertainty in predictions of sea level rise. Skepticism of prediction uncertainty would exist even when the physics is subjected to expert uncertainties. Such a model is considered weak. In the case of a strong model, it is commonly acknowledged that the model at the core of the COSSE contains all of the physics necessary to describe the climate but with some uncertainty that can be constrained by the mission’s data. Atmospheric models may fall into this category, with parameterized physics of longwave and shortwave radiation, clouds and convection.

What distinguishes a strong model from a weak model is the suspicion of structural uncertainty. Structural uncertainty is the statement that there exists a fundamental structural problem with a model that can conservatively be expected to prevent it from full consistency with existing data, no matter how the model is tuned. Methods do exist to account for structural error⁶. *Most importantly, suspicions of a weak model demand that auxiliary data be obtained for the sake of finding the structural error.* In Bayesian uncertainty quantification conditioned by a mission’s data, the evidence function—that is, the normalization factor for the posterior probability distribution—describes how well the model can describe the data that was obtained. See $E(\mathbf{d})$ in equation 8 of Appendix A. Any finding of structural error should eventually lead to the programming of a process study mission, one that will yield enough information to permit additional parameterized physics to strengthen the model.

Consideration of a model’s strength or weakness is important mostly for those missions that are inferential rather than empirical. In an inference mission the model is relied upon to form associations between data and the scientific objective. A COSSE for an empirical mission does not rely on a model in this way; however, it should expect a model to simulate variability well enough so that it can produce realistic estimations of sampling error.

⁶ N.B. “discrepancy”; Goldstein and Rougier, *SIAM J. Sci. Comput.*, **26**, 467–487, 2004.

3.3. Degree of sophistication

A COSSE always demands that a core model be able to simulate data and the well-defined scientific objective quantity. The simulators of the data and the scientific objective take the form of formulas that are coded and either incorporated into the core model inline or attached to the core model's output offline. There is only one way to implement code to generate the scientific objective quantity (by definition), but there are multiple ways to implement code to simulate the data of an observing system. Simulation of level 3 data is the least sophisticated, typically amounting to a dump of a geophysical variable in the core model. Simulation of level 2 is somewhat more sophisticated in that it requires subsampling the geophysical variable according to the sampling pattern of the observing system. Simulation of level 1b data requires a "forward" observation model to be attached to the climate model to simulate calibrated observations. For example, each member of the PPE should produce longwave or shortwave spectra, photons as a function of delay for lidar, or Doppler frequency for radio occultation. At its most sophisticated, simulation of level 1a would simulate realistic error in the basic measurement. Each level of sophistication has its own advantages and disadvantages.

Simulation of level 3 data is a level of sophistication that is likely best considered in the conceptual stage of mission development. It has the advantage of being the simplest to deploy in a COSSE in that it only requires that a geophysical variable be dumped to output. It has the disadvantage, though, of incomplete accounting for uncertainty in the remote sensing retrieval. In order to obtain a full accounting of uncertainty required of a COSSE, an observing system's science would be required to provide a complete description of retrieval error, subjecting the retrieval system to fully realistic simulations of measurements appropriate to the real Earth system. Without such a substantial independent effort by an observing system's science team, it is unlikely that objective determinations of science and measurement requirements will be obtained. At present it is standard practice for a proposing team to prove a retrieval capability in the form of a "theoretical basis", which can largely fulfill the requirement of connecting level 1 to level 3. The additional requirement of a COSSE framework is that the theoretical basis be demonstrated for the range of environments generated by the COSSE.

Simulation of level 2 data is an intermediate degree of sophistication. By subsampling model output to prospective sampling patterns, it becomes possible to specify requirements on mission architecture, mainly orbital selection and sampling density. It retains the advantages of a level 3 data simulator with only a minor addition to the climate model in the form of satellite subsampling of the output. Again, an independent effort would be needed to analyze retrieval error.

Simulation of level 1b data has all the advantages of simulating level 2 data but with an added advantage: it can be used to specify instrument requirements. Simulation of level 1b, which refers to well-calibrated measurements, allows the COSSE to determine whether an observing system's data types contain the information necessary for a mission to retrieve a targeted geophysical variable. Ordinarily, a mission proposal provides a demonstration of a retrieval capability in the form of an "algorithm theoretical basis", but with a COSSE that simulates level 1b, the retrieval capability is inherently demonstrated by the COSSE in an especially broad range of environmental conditions. The disadvantages become substantial, however. Simulation of level 1b radically increases the dimensionality of the data space, making it substantially more difficult to find the information content in the data that is relevant to the quantified scientific objective. As in §2.1, the *utility* and *quality* of an observing system is determined by a correlation ρ between quantified science objective and simulated data across all

members of the COSSE's PPE. Reducing the dimensionality of the data space down to a single dimension—to obtain a single correlation coefficient ρ —with little loss of information is an exercise that requires expert judgment and intuition.

Simulation of level 1a data adds the advantage of proper accounting for measurement error. While measurement error is frequently specified as a standard deviation independent of channel, for example, actual measurement error contains correlation and structure across a number of channels. A level 1a COSSE can place requirements on instrument parameters such as blackbody emissivity, clock error, etc. that is more appropriate to instrument manufacturing than a simpler accuracy and precision requirement. The disadvantage is daunting inasmuch as it may require a major augmentation of simulated output measurements and the implementation of complete retrieval systems.

In many cases, separate smaller scale models or observational input are used to determine simulation of retrieval errors in converting level 1b to level 2 geophysical measurements. An example would be using aircraft field experiment observations or high resolution large eddy simulator (LES) cloud models to provide input to radiative transfer instrument simulators to test cloud property retrieval methods. Meanwhile, global climate and or weather models might be used to determine orbit sampling uncertainties.

In general, COSSEs based on the simulation of level 3 data will be most useful for determining the *utility* of a geophysical variable in addressing the quantified science objective. COSSEs based on the simulation of level 2 data will be useful for specifying requirements on sampling patterns. As mentioned in §2.5, sampling uncertainties may be obtained from existing observations (e.g. geostationary observations for diurnal sampling requirements).

The degree of sophistication that is chosen will depend on the stage of the mission. Level 3 and level 2 simulation can occur at the mission concept stage, as can preliminary analysis of level 1b to level 2 retrieval uncertainties.

3.4. Complementarity vs. verification

It is clearly in NASA Earth Science's interest to address as broad a range of scientific objectives on climate as it can within a constrained budget, and so it makes sense that a single best approach is found to address an important scientific objective leaving other funds available to address other scientific objectives. This is the essence of *complementarity*. There is a class of observing system, though, that calls for diverse measurement types to observe the same geophysical variable in order to address a single important scientific objective. This is the essence of *verification*. These are two contradictory requirements of a program of Earth observation. When it is appropriate to consider complementarity as a requirement and when it is appropriate to consider verification as a requirement must be decided upon before evaluating *importance* of a proposed observing system.

An example of complementarity is when one measurement can constrain the integrated effect of a set of uncertain climate processes (e.g., sea level rise), while other measurements are needed to verify the component processes that lead to the integrated effect (e.g. ice sheet mass loss, ocean thermal expansion, and mountain glacier ice loss). A similar example exists for cloud feedback with an integrated effect of changing cloud radiative forcing versus the component changes in cloud physical properties that lead to the changing cloud radiative effects. Yet another example is the case of net radiative balance of the Earth. In this case, the most effective observation at long time scales (a decade or longer) is the in-situ ARGO ocean float

network measurement of changes in ocean heat storage, while the most effective measurement of seasonal and inter-annual time scales is from satellite broadband radiation budget observations.

The issue of verification is best viewed in the context of validation of an observing system's measurements when the measurement requirements are far more stringent than any existing system can provide, hence making the traditional step of limited-scale validation insufficient. In such cases, the alternative to measurement validation is scientific verification. The class of observing system for which this is directly applicable encompasses inference missions that test climate models. See §3.1. These observing systems require accuracy that is so extreme that its measurements cannot be validated by traditional methods. Instead, the only way to assure credibility in the anomalies and trends in the geophysical variables that are the scientific objectives is to compare them to the anomalies and trends inferred from another, independent observing system. If the anomalies and trends are the same, then the objective results will be trusted. It is the only way to validate such observing systems. This is the approach used by metrology laboratories for the definition and maintenance of high accuracy international physical standards (SI).

When verification is the standard by which an observing system is rated for *utility*, the *a priori* of uncertainty quantification changes. Instead of accounting for all prior data in the formulation of the Bayesian prior, all data is accounted for except that data collected by a contemporaneous redundant observing system.

It may seem extravagant to spend substantial resources on verification, but if a multi-decadal climate monitoring system yields a scientific result that is surprising, the unavailability of a redundant observing system will render the results incredible and useless to the climate research community. Verification can be thought of as independent verification, which increases confidence, sometimes dramatically, in scientific results.

3.5. Prediction vs. hypothesis testing

There is a fundamental difference between climate observing systems that seek a strict hypothesis test and those oriented toward improving climate prediction capability. In a strict hypothesis test, a small number of hypotheses of the climate are proposed and an experiment is devised that determines which is the most correct. In improving climate prediction, a new observation is obtained that reduces some uncertainty in unknown physics of a climate model. See §2.2.

The consequences for a COSSE are important. In the process of quantifying uncertainty, missions of climate prediction are valued according to their ability to reduce uncertainty from *a priori* to *a posteriori* distributions of the scientific objective, which is determined by the factor $(1 - \rho^2)^{1/2}$. It is a computation that can be accomplished with a single core model with variable physics. Observing systems intended for hypothesis testing, however, are valued according to their ability to distinguish between a few competing hypotheses. Its COSSE requires a PPE for multiple core models, each core model implementing the physics of one of the competing hypotheses. A COSSE for such an observing system does not provide a single number for its utility and quality. Instead, only a statement concerning whether or not the distributions of observations produced— $O(A)$ for a PPE for hypothesis A , $O(B)$ for the PPE for hypothesis B , and so on—overlap.

4. COSSE key capabilities

A NASA COSSE can provide objective and quantified determinations of mission, scientific and instrument requirements for an Earth observing system and of the *utility* and *quality* of the observing system depending on those requirements. Many recent developments in climate modeling, detection and attribution of climate change, and NASA satellite missions are pointing in the direction of a COSSE. In an environment in which the demands for observing many and varied aspects of the Earth's environmental system exceed the institutional financial resources to satisfy all demands, an approach to selecting among a wide range of proposed missions that is fair and objective should be highly desirable to the NASA Earth Science Program.

It is understood that a climate program must embrace different types of missions. Some missions will be oriented toward process studies, others toward long-term monitoring. All could potentially benefit from a COSSE at the various stages of missions' maturity. Below is a list of key capabilities of COSSEs:

- A capability to simulate the complex natural systems that influence concentrations of aerosol, anthropogenic greenhouse gases, ozone, and pollutants in the Earth's atmosphere, including interactions of the biosphere and ocean chemistry at the surface-air boundary;
- A capability to simulate the radiative impacts of aerosol and anthropogenic greenhouse gases and land use changes;
- A capability to simulate the complex dynamics and thermodynamics of the ocean and atmosphere, including clouds;
- A capability to simulate the hydrological cycle including soil moisture, precipitation, run-off, floods, and droughts;
- A capability to simulate the complicated processes of the cryosphere, from the mid- and low latitude mountain glaciers to the sea and land-based ice of the Arctic and Antarctic, as it impacts the global environment, especially sea level rise;
- A capability to simulate a wide variety of satellite observations of the Earth's environment, active and passive, from microwave to ultraviolet, limb-sounding to nadir-sounding;
- A capability to simulate realistic satellite sampling patterns, with dependences on footprint size, on the scanning pattern and sampling density, and on the diurnal cycle;
- A capability to simulate in situ measurement of the environment;
- A capability to predict decadal, multi-decadal, and multi-century trends of the Earth's climate system;
- A capability to predict changes in extreme weather relevant to the U.S.: hurricane intensity and landfall frequency, mesoscale and strong convection, and heat waves, frequency of floods and droughts;
- A capability to model the climate system at varying degrees of complexity, from full Earth system models to models of intermediate complexity and advanced energy balance models;

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- A capability to quantify uncertainty in data simulations and in predictions following the rules of Bayesian uncertainty quantification;
- An opportunity to bridge the gap between the cultures of modeling and of observation in the NASA Earth Science community;
- A capability to simulate both simple and complex components of the climate system, including anthropogenic greenhouse gas and aerosol concentrations, distributions and radiative impacts, land use change, volcanic forcing, and solar irradiance change;
- A capability to quantify the uncertainty associated with a wide range of components of the climate system in a way that spans an expert uncertainty in those components;
- A capability to recognize and possibly quantify structural uncertainty in models of the Earth system; and
- *A mandate for specific, detailed quantifiable scientific objectives of proposed missions and observing systems.*

The capabilities pertain to the climate model or process models at the core of the COSSE, the need to simulate a wide variety of data types, and the ability to generate disparate scientific objectives based on the output of climate models. The data types must span data types that are sensitive to thermodynamic variables, surface properties, winds, clouds, aerosol, constituent concentrations, and radiation fields. The scientific objectives can pertain to pure climate science, such as change in circulation and hydrological cycle, or to societal objectives, such as climate sensitivity and carbon emission limits, drought and flood, spread of disease, forced migration, and coastal flooding. In some cases, the forward modeling capability is simple and for others a forward model requires development. The generation of scientific objectives related to societal objectives will almost always require development in the form of connecting social or economic models to climate models.

5. Examples of previous OSSEs

OSSEs have been performed previously, albeit in very limited cases, and most often not for climate science topics. The most commonly applied OSSE is in numerical weather prediction. COSSEs have mostly been performed in the context of sampling studies. Thorough uncertainty quantification in the light of previous data has been used to better constrain distributions of climate sensitivity⁷, but the same efforts have not been exercised in the context of prospective mission evaluation. Examples of COSSEs that have been performed for climate missions include:

- TRMM⁸ and GPM for precipitation sampling uncertainty⁹
- Radiation budget for orbit sampling uncertainty¹⁰
- Cloud 3-D effects for MODIS retrievals of optical depth retrievals (using LES models, Landsat cloud fields) and sea surface temperatures¹¹,

⁷ D.M.H. Sexton et al., *Climate Dynamics*, **38**, 2513–2542, 2012.

⁸ Bell et al., *J. Appl. Meteor.*, **40**, 938–954, 2001.

⁹ Iida et al., *Geophys. Res. Lett.*, **33**, doi:10.1029/2005GL024910, 2006.

¹⁰ G.L. Smith, *IEEE Trans. Geosci. Rem. Sensing*, **53**, 1656–1665, 2015.

- Altimeter for ocean current uncertainty¹²
- ARGO for deep ocean temperature change sampling uncertainty¹³
- CLARREO orbit sampling for zonal and global mean reflected solar and infrared spectra.
- CLARREO spectral fingerprinting of climate change: using models and observations¹⁴
- OCO-2 uncertainty in determination of CO₂ sources and sinks¹⁵
- Downscaled brightness temperature/soil moisture for SMAP^{16,17}

6. Examples of future COSSEs

Most efforts that can be classified as COSSEs to date have been simplistic implementations of sampling studies. Obvious applications of more complete COSSEs in the future can be envisioned. Illustrative examples include, but by no means are limited to:

- Aerosol indirect effect COSSEs. How to go about measuring or constraining the aerosol indirect effect is a problem that has eluded the climate community for decades despite its long recognized importance to the evolution of climate. New methods can potentially aid in the simulation of measurements related to the aerosol indirect effect. Such methods include the multi-scale modeling framework (MMF) or large eddy simulators (LES) embedded in the Goddard Chemistry Aerosol Radiation and Transport (GOCART) model. Candidate instruments are those of ACE: lidar, radar, radiometer and polarimeter. A COSSE appropriately implemented can determine how well such instruments deployed ideally can infer the aerosol indirect effect.
- Aerosol direct effect COSSEs. A COSSE to determine how to measure the aerosol direct effect would entail an advanced capability to simulate the effect in a complex meteorological environment but focus on the ability of geophysical retrieval. What complement of measurement technologies is necessary to infer the aerosol direct effect? Possibilities include a high spectral resolution lidar (HSRL), polarimetry, shortwave spectra.
- Particulate fine matter COSSEs. Missions are underway to measure fine particulate matter in the boundary layer, but how well it can be predicted is an open question.
- Climate sensitivity and multi-century climate prediction COSSEs. Equilibrium climate sensitivity remains one of the most important implicit properties of the climate system that remains and one of the most elusive to measure. Extraordinary effort has been put into constraining its uncertainty with limited success. Contemporary thought holds that

¹¹ Liu and Minnett, *Rem. Sens. Environ.*, **177**, 48–64, 2016.

¹² J.C. Marshall, *J. Phys. Ocean.*, **15**, 330–349, 1985.

¹³ Hadfield et al., *J. Geophys. Res.*, **112**, doi:10.1029/2006JC003825, 2007.

¹⁴ Huang et al., *J. Geophys. Res.*, **115**, doi:10.1029/2009JD012766, 2010; Feldman et al., *Geosci. Model Dev.*, **8**, 1943–1954, 2015.

¹⁵ Baker et al., *Atmos. Chem. Phys.*, **10**, 4145–4165, 2010.

¹⁶ Das et al., *IEEE Trans. Geosci. Rem. Sensing*, **54**, 640–650, 2016.

¹⁷ Piles et al., *IEEE Trans. Geosci. Rem. Sensing*, **47**, 4125–4131, 2009.

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horizontal fluxes of energy in the atmosphere and the ocean hinder the inference of climate sensitivity for decadal scale observation¹⁷; thus, a COSSE focused on climate sensitivity almost certainly will require a fully coupled ocean-atmosphere model at its core.

- Global cloud feedback COSSE. Cloud feedback is the least constrained of the radiative feedbacks in the climate system. Attention has been paid to stratocumulus clouds over the eastern subtropical oceans as indicators of the size of the cloud radiative feedback¹⁸, but a substantially more rigorous COSSE with cloud feedback as a scientific objective will be necessary to arrive at an appropriate observing system that places strong constraints on it.
- Sea level rise COSSE. The major contributors to sea level rise are the melting of polar land-based ice, melting of mid-latitude glaciers, and thermal expansion of the oceans. Thus, a COSSE to develop a predictive capability for sea level rise must include a credible cryospheric component attached to a fully coupled atmosphere-ocean climate model. In this case a COSSE must obtain auxiliary data for the sake of discovering unforeseen physics in the climate system related to sea level rise because ice sheet models are in the early stages of development.
- Carbon cycle COSSEs. Subjective and quantitative work has gone into the design of forest-scale carbon budgeting¹⁹. Global scale carbon budgeting will require a link between forest- and field-scale carbon monitoring and satellite monitoring.
- Global precipitation COSSE. Weather forecasts of precipitation and long-term climatological prediction of precipitation have always been goals of high importance to NASA Earth Science, yet no single observing system is sufficient for all precipitation objectives. A COSSE that can address predictability of precipitation on many scales and what observing systems would best enable the research should be a high priority. For what purposes are satellite and surface radar, and geostationary infrared most valuable? What coverage is needed? How can Doppler radar and multi-wavelength radar improve precipitation measurements and forecasts? Are field experiments and field experiment COSSEs using cloud resolving models with explicitly resolve microphysics, the first step toward such a goal?
- Extreme weather COSSE. Recent decadal scale trends in drought in the U.S. may or may not be attributable to global warming. The same is true of tornado outbreaks and inland flooding. Near-term predictability of extreme weather is an observational issue for NWP. Seasonal to decadal scale predictability of extremes may be due to large scale radiative imbalances, shifts in storm tracks, or changes in the hydrological cycle. Sampling requirements for extremes may be very different than those for climate change averages.

¹⁷ K.C. Armour et al., *J. Climate*, **26**, 4518–4534, 2013.

¹⁸ S. Bony et al., *J. Climate*, **19**, 3445–3482, 2006.

¹⁹ *Field Measurements for Forest Carbon Monitoring: A Landscape-Scale Approach*, C.M. Hoover, Ed., Springer, New York, 2008.

7. Outstanding issues for a COSSE for NASA Earth Sciences

The central capabilities a COSSE offers to the NASA Earth Sciences community are to provide objective and transparent determinations of measurement requirements and to evaluate the utility and quality of prospective observing systems. Much remains unknown about how to go about implementing a COSSE capability in NASA Earth Sciences.

7.1. Who should perform a COSSE?

A COSSE can be performed either by a proposing mission team or by an independent organization. Advantages and disadvantages exist in either approach. A COSSE performed by a proposing science team has the advantages of being undertaken by experts in understanding instrument characteristics and level 1b to level 2 retrieval algorithms. It has the disadvantage of potential lack of objectivity or a strong perception thereof, because it is possible to distort COSSE results by not accounting for all relevant uncertain physics in the climate system, and a proposing mission science team may have “confirmation bias” that leads to this effect despite the most conscientious efforts. This suggests that just as for any normal journal paper, that COSSE results would not be considered valid until accepted by a peer reviewed journal or are reviewed by an independent NASA appointed review panel.

A COSSE performed by an independent institution has the advantage of objectivity and the disadvantage of reduced expertise in the instrument and retrieval algorithm. If the independent institution is in fact the same NASA center that has proposed the mission previously, then the same element of real or perceived confirmation bias may exist as for the proposing science team itself. In all cases, independent peer review will remain essential to minimize the influence of conflict of interest and confirmation bias.

Considerable investment is likely required to develop a COSSE tailored to an individual mission concept. Following the discussion in section 3.3, however, it may often be possible to separate COSSE results for the *utility* of a geophysical measurement and the *quality* of its orbit sampling requirements from COSSEs to evaluate the *quality* of algorithms to retrieve the geophysical variable from level 1b data.

7.2. How many and which models should be used at the core of a COSSE?

There are approximately 20 independent climate models worldwide, and four of them are domestic (NASA, NOAA, NSF, DOE). Which one should be used at the core of a COSSE? A more complete climate model might seem obvious as a candidate for a core model because it accounts for more physics of the climate system; however, such a model may be far too computationally expensive to be of use in a COSSE. Models of intermediate and lesser complexity also exist and may be suited to a COSSE. Should NASA Earth Sciences make a suite of such models available to the research community? Moreover, structural uncertainty does exist in each model, so it may prove worthwhile to implement more than one climate model as a core model.

The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change of the U.N. has organized climate model ensembles of opportunity for its last two scientific assessments, which are known as the Climate Model Inter-comparison Projects (CMIPs). All of the world’s sophisticated climate models generated a prescribed set of scenario experiments and generated a prescribed set of outputs for the sake of inter-comparison. The ensembles are small, but the members are as independent of one another in their numerical implementation and physics as can be reasonably

expected. The differences between them are the results of uncertain physics in climate modeling and structural uncertainty. A climate model ensemble of opportunity such as this can be used to evaluate the degree to which uncertainty quantification by any single climate model is constrained by its own structural limitations.

7.3. What level of sophistication should be considered in COSSEs? Should the level of sophistication increase as a mission matures?

Because few resources exist in the development of mission concepts, it is almost certainly an added burden to a proposing science team to have to undertake an overly sophisticated COSSE. In the early phase of mission development, a far less sophisticated COSSE would be necessary to demonstrate the value of a mission. During and after the completion of a mission, a more sophisticated COSSE would be useful to yielding final scientific results as well as determining if further advances in capability are required.

7.4. Should a COSSE infrastructure be centralized or distributed?

A COSSE infrastructure can be comprised of several components, including the core model, computing and storage facilities, auxiliary data sets, data simulators, and personnel with expertise in climate modeling and prediction. On one hand, domestic climate models and the groups that have developed them have already assembled the infrastructure necessary to a COSSE; however, the same groups may be overwhelmed by new demands placed on them for COSSE products. Every proposing science team would need to consult and collaborate with a COSSE group from the earliest through the most mature stages of their mission profile, and less than satisfactory (yet objective) findings might well create protracted political difficulties. On the other hand, if domestic climate models and their supporting data sets are made easily transferrable, the specific expertise that is necessary for a particular instance of an OSSE will be provided by the proposing science team. One implementation of a PPE has already been constructed so as to be easily transferrable²⁰.

An alternative approach would be to allow science teams to form collaborations with any climate modeling group interested in supporting and developing the COSSE effort. In this approach a ROSES COSSE research program would solicit proposals from joint observation/modeling teams to develop COSSE capabilities. These proposals would be competitively reviewed as for other ROSES proposal calls, with the highest rated proposals receiving funding. Following an initial 3-year award, follow-on support would depend on a second round of proposals based on the level of progress in the initial grant period, journal papers published, and proposed advances in the second grant period. Such ROSES calls might require that successful proposals provide open access COSSE tools such as COSP instrument simulators currently used in the climate modeling community and shared across climate models. A benefit of the alternative approach is that it may engage climate modeling researchers to consider the types of measurements that are most critical for addressing their modeling needs, especially with respect to outstanding scientific questions that they seek to address with their modeling efforts.

These questions will need to be addressed by a combination of research and expert discussion. Different models, even the domestic ones, behave very differently from one another when their physics are perturbed, and persistent issues of model drift and model calibration add a

²⁰ *ClimatePrediction.net*.

further degree of complexity to a COSSE. Such issues can be addressed through a short-term and small research program such as one offered through ROSES, regardless of whether a centralized or distributed program (or a combination) is decided on.

7.5. When are COSSEs of limited utility?

There are cases where COSSEs are not an appropriate approach. Those cases come about when no data simulator exists, when the core model is not suited to producing predictions of the scientific objective, or when uncertainty in the core model does not subjectively capture consensus uncertainty of the scientific community. As models mature, COSSEs become more useful. The lack of relevant models for COSSE experiments may also suggest the need for model development specifically targeted at enabling future COSSE capability, possibly through the Modeling and Analysis Program.

8. First steps toward a NASA Earth Science COSSE capability

The value to NASA Earth Science that can be provided by a COSSE and the implications for climate science are clear. The steps toward implementation depend upon significant decisions that must be made, as listed in §7. Before the most basic questions are answered, two first steps could provide critical information to evaluate the utility of the concept: (1) a symposium could be organized in which climate scientists with experience appropriate to the construction of COSSEs and prominent climate scientists and program managers interested in its utility gather to discuss how to proceed, and (2) a one-time call for a ROSES program could be considered to form exploratory teams to perform preliminary research into the viability of a COSSE. The foremost question to be addressed is whether a COSSE program in NASA should be centralized or decentralized or some combination of the two. If a centralized effort appears to be most advantageous, then NASA Earth Sciences could consider initiating the organization of a COSSE Office. If a decentralized effort appears to be preferable, then NASA Earth Sciences could consider developing a continuing ROSES program that supports a variety of institutions and mission science teams in developing their own COSSEs. Appendix B, §11, lists a cursory comparison of the advantages of disadvantages of a centralized vs. a decentralized COSSE program. The next sections discuss possible first steps that could be considered, as well as discussion of a centralized vs. decentralized COSSE program for NASA Earth Sciences.

8.1. Special symposium and discussion

It would be advisable if the questions raised here and in §7 above were first addressed before development of a COSSE capability or a call for research to frame the initiative is considered. Toward this end, it is recommended that a special symposium and discussion group be formed to decide on a framework for the development of a NASA COSSE program.

The attendees of such a symposium could be selected to represent several aspects of the COSSE initiative. They could include

- Climate scientists who have previously undertaken a PPE,
- Members of the climate modeling community, including those with COSSE experience,
- Experts in the field of Bayesian uncertainty quantification for climate,

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- Scientists from existing mission science teams with expertise in the information content of data,
- Members of the numerical weather prediction community who have previously performed OSSEs,
- Computer scientists with experience in developing the infrastructure for a PPE, and
- Officials of the NASA Earth Science Program Office.

This white paper could possibly serve as working material for the meeting. One potential outcome of the meeting would be a technical memorandum to NASA on plans for proceeding with a COSSE development. Should NASA agree to the findings and consider providing funding for a COSSE, then the plans could be announced to the greater climate community through a suitable publication such as the *Bulletin of the American Meteorological Society* and a ROSES opportunity could be developed.

The symposium should also suggest some early deliverables in the first 5 years of development that could be used to judge progress and usefulness of an expanded COSSE capability.

8.2. An initial ROSES call for preliminary research

An initial ROSES call for preliminary research could go to proposals that directly address the questions posed in §7. An initial annual budget of, for example, ~\$3 million would be used to support a ROSES call for 3-year COSSE proposals. The outcome would be an understanding of how domestic climate models behave when subjected to perturbed physics, a model infrastructure that can easily accept inline code pertaining to forward models for observations and orbit simulators, examinations of statistical methods in analyzing the output of COSSEs, and rudimentary COSSEs for some primitive science questions such as multi-decadal global temperature change. Awards could range from, e.g., \$100K per year to \$300K per year depending on the amount of effort necessary to accomplish the objectives of the proposal. Meetings could be held annually to discuss progress and provide opportunities for collaboration and future directions. Research findings would be published in peer-reviewed journals. Midway through the program, a report would be delivered to NASA Earth Sciences regarding the viability of an extended program in COSSEs.

8.3. Scope for a COSSE capability as NASA internal infrastructure

An independent office for COSSEs within the NASA Earth Science Program would have its own advantages. It would allow NASA to assemble a team with the special expertise that will be required of a COSSE, to construct COSSEs in a more transparent, objective, and fair manner. A COSSE office would also allow an accumulation of knowledge of the inner workings of uncertainty in a particular climate model, and could potentially improve consistency across all implementations of a COSSE. Finally, a COSSE office may allow more rapid response to NASA HQ directed studies that result from unexpected mission failures, budget changes, or administration direction.

The foundation of a COSSE office would be one or more core global climate models subjected to perturbed physics. New proposals for observing systems would lead to a variety of developments to the NASA COSSE:

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- A regional or smaller scale model for observing systems oriented to process studies or small-scale phenomena;
- A prescription of the expert judgments on the regional model's own uncertain physics;
- An appropriate instrument simulator that can be coded inline with the core global model or regional model; and
- A prescription of measurement uncertainties.

The principles of PPEs allow the perturbations of the physics in the global model and of the physics of an embedded regional model to be imposed simultaneously. Most global climate models have already developed capabilities such as this in the form of dynamical downscaling. Dynamical downscaling can be serially embedded in theory, even down to cloud-resolving scales. Dynamical downscaling creates discontinuities at the boundaries of the embedded higher spatial resolution regions because the physics of the atmosphere depends upon spatial resolution in ways that are not fully understood. Eventual insertion and implementation of dynamical downscaling thus remains a topic for modeling research. Multiple instrument simulators can be implemented for a given member of a PPE. Each instrument simulator would be defined by its orbit, its sampling pattern, footprint size, spectral range and resolution, etc. The effects of measurements uncertainties, specifically imprecision and inaccuracy, can be added to the simulated data offline.

There are three potential disadvantages of a centralized COSSE Office. First, if the COSSE Office is established in a single NASA Center, there will be the concern of potential conflict of interest for COSSE simulations of mission concepts at the COSSE center versus concepts from other organizations within or outside NASA. This group would need to be walled off from center management to minimize such issues. Even in this case, appearance of conflict of interest may exist even in the absence of actual conflict of interest. Second, there is a risk that the COSSE Office becomes isolated and driven by its own interests above those of the broader research community. Third, a COSSE Office limits the diversity of expertise that can be applied to that existing at the COSSE Office and not the broader modeling and observation research community.

Developing COSSE capability as a core NASA internal competency would require initial selection of Earth model types to begin development of the capability. The domestic climate models that could serve as cores for the OSSE are the NCAR Community Earth System Model (CESM), the NASA GISS Earth System Model, the GFDL Earth System Model (GFDL ESM2), and the DOE Accelerated Climate Model for Energy (ACME). Some of these models are already portable and need only be compiled on high-performance computing clusters. Limited PPEs have already been generated for a few of these models, but no exhaustive study has yet been performed. Because every climate model contains its own structural uncertainty, retaining two models of vastly independent heritage as core models in a COSSE would be a wise policy. Also, comparisons of uncertainty between ensembles of opportunity and perturbed physics of a single model should provide valuable information on structural uncertainty in any given model.

Once the Earth model and mission/instrument simulation types would be chosen, it must be configured in a way that makes the incorporation of inline regional models, data simulators, and instrument simulators seamless and transparent. A basic set of data simulators in the form of radiative transfer models would be implemented at the global scale. These simulators would be selected based on computational efficiency, accuracy, and flexibility (e.g. spectral resolution,

viewing geometry, etc.). Because no single modeling center has the expertise to build all aspects of a centralized COSSE, it will be necessary to create a program that rotates scientific staff through the COSSE Office in order to develop the COSSE to meet all of its demands.

Where the NASA COSSE Office would reside is an open question. NASA centers that host existing models are possibilities as would be already existing offices within NASA Earth Science.

8.4. A decentralized COSSE program

The big picture of a decentralized COSSE program has each mission science team implementing its own COSSE. The COSSE would be required of every new mission proposal and should provide the information necessary to evaluate its utility and quality. The proposing team would leverage its own expertise in models that simulate the phenomena it proposes to address, in forward models that simulate its data, and the likely error characteristics of its instruments. The core model of its PPE would be implemented by collaboration with a climate modeling center or by transferring it to the proposing team's computing facilities. A peer-reviewed publication would be necessary to guarantee that uncertainty is fully quantified and the statistics are performed correctly.

The greatest advantages of a decentralized COSSE program would be the availability of the expertise needed to model the climate and the data and for creating an environment in which a broad range of diverse ideas on COSSE experiments would result from the sheer number that would be implemented. The prime disadvantage of a decentralized COSSE program would be the difficulty of guaranteeing objectivity of COSSE results. Different models used as the cores of the COSSE experiments could easily lead to differing structures and sized of uncertainty quantification that could bias results. Colloquially, a review panel could end up in a situation in which it is comparing apples and oranges rather than objective determinations of *utility* and *quality*. A problem such as this could be addressed by prescribing the requirements of every COSSE experiment done for observing system proposals. Requirements would include the specific core global climate model that should be used, its uncertainties that must be perturbed, what regional models should be embedded and how their physics should be perturbed. In fact, NASA Earth Sciences might consider developing a transferrable COSSE modeling system to be made available to mission design and development teams.

Funding for a decentralized COSSE program within NASA Earth Sciences could be carried out through a continuing ROSES program, governed by a NASA HQ Program Manager. The manager would design the ROSES COSSE call for proposals, select and run a review panel for proposal selection, and verify progress through reports and journal papers published. COSSE information in preparation for a Decadal Survey could also be handled in this manner: both for past selected instruments/missions and for new proposed instruments/missions. All resource management for a selected proposal would be handled by the P.I., including decisions on prioritization of computer system and personnel resources, COSSE design changes, and publication decisions. Independent review would be done through peer review of published COSSE studies. NASA HQ, the NASA centers, and the science community are all already familiar with this governance model and would likely support it.

The essential role of the ROSES COSSE Program would be to provide support for science teams to initiate COSSEs, to allow NASA HQ to request specific COSSE studies, develop modeling tools that can be incorporated into easily transferrable climate model packages suited to PPEs, and continue basic research into the theoretical basis for COSSEs. For example,

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it would include support for the development of instrument simulators similar to the existing COSP tools for ISCCP cloud properties, Cloudsat radar return vertical profile, and CALIPSO lidar vertical backscatter profile. Others might provide for connection of climate models to economic and human ecology models in order to broaden the scope of the relationship between societal and scientific objectives for a COSSE program.

Awards for COSSE theory and development for three-year grants could be, e.g., \$150K to \$300K per year. Awards for radiative transfer and instrument simulator tools could be, e.g., \$100K to \$200K per year. Research efforts are expected to publish results in the peer reviewed literature to maintain objectivity and reliability of results. In the case of instrument simulators, the resulting software package should be delivered to the COSSE Program Manager. It might reasonably be expected that ultimately this program might grow to a similar size as the other R&A programs (\$5 to \$10M/yr.).

8.5. General questions

It is most likely that the number of potential COSSE studies would far exceed the OSSE funding or centralized capability. As a result, there are a wide range of prioritization decisions that will need to be made including:

- What fraction of the COSSE computer capacity (processors, storage) is allocated to a single COSSE effort?
- Could COSSE PPEs be defined in such a way as to support a wide variety of individual COSSE efforts? This could minimize costs, but might lead to much more detailed model output (e.g. higher time/space resolution of model fields, larger number of output model variables) and therefore much higher data storage requirements. The balance would likely be the costs of model processing capability versus the cost of data storage.
- What defines a single COSSE effort? A single instrument and spacecraft? A pre-phase A mission of multiple instruments and spacecraft and launch vehicles? For example, would the 2007 Decadal Survey ACE mission be considered a single COSSE or multiple COSSEs?
- What fraction of COSSE manpower capacity is allocated to a single COSSE effort? What if one COSSE requires 5 times the capability as another COSSE? How are resources allocated?
- Who decides which COSSEs are to be performed if applications for COSSEs exceed resources? Who decides what order they are performed?
- What happens when an instrument scientist wants COSSE design changes made because he didn't like the initial results? How long can he keep demanding changes? What about the impact of delays on COSSE studies waiting in the queue? What if the new changes require much larger resources than were planned?
- Who submits journal articles on the COSSE results? Who gets to decide which COSSE results should be published and which should not be published? If the initial results are bad, but might improve with an COSSE or mission design change, are the original results published? There is potential for a lot of angst between instrument P.I.s and a centralized COSSE organization. What happens in the case of a disagreement between NASA HQ,

the instrument P.I. and the NASA centralized COSSE organization on whether to publish OSSE results?

- What if NASA HQ or a NASA Center Director wants an COSSE performed: are other COSSE studies underway put on hold? How are priorities set?
- Is there an independent board to make prioritization decisions if the COSSE capability resides at one center? Does NASA HQ have a program scientist who serves this function? Or does a NASA HQ program scientist run a ROSES call for OSSE studies and select them using science panels similar to other ROSES research grants?

9. Can NASA COSSE organization lessons be learned from other organization functions that cross disciplines?

If a NASA COSSE program took the form as a centralized facility, then a number of possible models for the COSSE office can be considered. See Table 1 for a brief summary. Below is a discussion of three possibilities that are likely most relevant for a COSSE office within NASA Earth Sciences. Discussions concerning the form of the COSSE program, and Table 1 itself, should take place at the symposium mentioned in §8.1.

9.1. Aerospace Corporation and RAO independent cost studies

These organizations bring independent instrument and mission cost estimation expertise to provide independent cost estimates, primarily based on analogs to past instruments, spacecraft, launch systems, data systems, and science/algorithm analysis. These analyses can be requested and funded by NASA HQ (e.g. as part of a Decadal Survey study process) or can be requested and funded by a mission concept team in pre-phase A. There are no competitive proposals for this process. Nothing similar to a ROSES call has ever been used. The reason for this is the typically short time scale of the study (weeks to a month or two) vs. the much longer time scale of the competitive process, along with the very limited sources of such services. RAO is a group of NASA civil servants “walled off” at GSFC from their normal administrative processes to try to provide some independence from GSFC management interests. The Aerospace Corporation is a private aerospace company that provides costing services and expertise to both NASA and DoD space missions. Both groups rely heavily on databases of past mission costs.

There is limited interaction between the mission teams and either Aerospace Corporation or RAO. In fact, they often seem like a “black box”. They are given information on mission characteristics such as instruments, spacecraft, orbit, launch vehicle, data system, and deliver an independent cost estimate. It is not so much a collaboration as an independent sanity check on cost estimates.

Given the extensive collaboration required, the long time scale to develop, implement, and publish COSSE studies (typically 2 to 3 years), and the much larger cost of such services, it seems unlikely that the Aerospace Corporation or RAO organization models are relevant “analogs” for developing an improved NASA COSSE capability.

9.2. Instrument/mission design laboratory studies

These organizations bring together science and engineering expertise to explore the trade space of instrument and mission design. They are “institutional” in that they are run primarily by NASA civil servants and by local support contract personnel at a given NASA center. JPL,

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GSFC, and LaRC all have versions of this capability. A typical design lab study takes about 1 week and runs as an integrated short term “tiger team” of expertise in the required science and engineering functions. Staff either dedicates full time to such a design lab, or they are “borrowed” occasionally from their other activities for a short time period. The entire exercise takes place over one to a few weeks in time, depending on the objective of the design lab. The cost of such studies is modest. There is no competition to select who performs the studies. Studies are funded and initiated by NASA HQ, a NASA Center, a pre-phase A mission, or an ad-hoc group of researchers with a new mission concept it wants to understand better. The Design Labs do have some permanent infrastructure: typically, a specially designed room to assist in the real time collaboration process, special software tools for mission design, and administrative staff that support the basic capability.

Given the extensive collaboration and iteration required, the long time scale to develop, implement, and publish COSSE studies (typically 2 to 3 years), and the much larger cost of such services, it seems unlikely that the Instrument/Mission Design Lab organization models are relevant “analogs” for developing an improved NASA COSSE capability.

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Table 1. Example Organizational Models for NASA OSSE Capability

(green = straightforward, yellow = more challenging, red = most challenging)

Organization Name	Conflict of Interest Issues?	Science Expertise Required	Users of the Capability	Stakeholders and Funders
RAO ICE	walled off to minimize	engineering costing	NASA HQ/PI/Center	NASA HQ directed program
Aerospace ICE	n/a	engineering costing	NASA HQ/PI/Center	NASA HQ/PI/Center funding
GMAO	no, NASA infrastructure	weather modeling/assimilation	NOAA, Science Community	NASA HQ directed funding
NASA GISS climate model	no, NASA infrastructure	climate modeling	Science Community	NASA HQ directed funding
MODIS data product team	no, peer reviewed proposals	earth science algorithm & data systems	Science Community	NASA HQ facility instrument ROSES call, DAACs
CERES or MISR data products	no, peer reviewed EOS teams	earth science algorithm & data systems	Science Community	NASA HQ PI instrument phase E, DAACs
DAACs	yes until they became distributed	data systems	Instrument Leads, NASA HQ, Science Community	NASA HQ PI mission leads (SIPS)
PCMDI	no, science community service	climate modeling and data systems	Climate Science Community	DOE HQ
NCAR Climate Model	no, science community service	climate modeling	Climate Science Community	NSF
ECMWF	no, unique Euro organization	weather modeling/assimilation	International weather prediction, Science community.	Europe 20 nations
Informal OSSEs	yes until peer reviewed papers	observation science & modeling science	PI, NASA HQ, Centers, Science Community	mission leads in pre-phase A thru B, pre-phase A decadal survey missions
NASA ROSES OSSEs	no if peer reviewed proposals and papers	observation science & modeling science	PI, NASA HQ, Centers, Science Community	NASA HQ ROSES call
NASA Directed OSSE Program	yes, for OSSE institution	observation science & modeling science	PI, NASA HQ, Centers, Science Community	NASA HQ directed OSSE program

10. Appendix A: Theory of a COSSE

A climate OSSE (COSSE) is implemented by considering all sources of uncertainty in measurement and development of a model that incorporates all of them. The uncertain model physics that we desire the observations to improve are considered using perturbations made to a vector α subject to relevant research expert estimates of uncertainty in the physical parameters. Some of the parameters include the initial state of the climate system; when they are perturbed, different realizations of natural variability are obtained. Others are parameters in the parameterized physics of the climate system. The probability distribution that describes the uncertainty space of α is $Pe(\alpha)$. The core climate model generates a time series of prognostic and diagnostic variables that are needed to simulate data that are ultimately determined by the parameters α : Perfect data \mathbf{x} are simulated by a forward model $\mathbf{x} = \mathcal{D}(\alpha)$ and the science objective y is generated from the same parameters $y = \mathcal{M}(\alpha)$. In a COSSE, a joint distribution of data and science objective is formed:

$$Pr(\mathbf{x}, y) = \int \delta(\mathbf{x} - \mathcal{D}(\alpha)) \delta(y - \mathcal{M}(\alpha)) Pe(\alpha) d\alpha. \quad (1)$$

A priori uncertainty in the science objective is the joint distribution marginalized in y :

$$Pr_y(y) = \int Pr(\mathbf{x}, y) d\mathbf{x} = \int \delta(y - \mathcal{M}(\alpha)) Pe(\alpha) d\alpha. \quad (2)$$

The requirements on the observations (accuracy, precision, sampling error) must be substantially narrower than the a priori distribution on the observables:

$$Pr_x(\mathbf{x}) = \int Pr(\mathbf{x}, y) dy = \int \delta(\mathbf{x} - \mathcal{D}(\alpha)) Pe(\alpha) d\alpha. \quad (3)$$

By varying the initial state only in the parameters space α , the accuracy requirement dictates that the overall uncertainty be less than the naturally occurring internal variability of the climate system, which is generated in an ensemble by only perturbing the initial state. Effectively, this is how the measurement requirements for the climate monitoring mission CLARREO were determined. By varying the initial state *and* the uncertain physics of the climate system, the measurement requirements become less stringent than those dictated solely by internal variability if the observations have previously been proven to be of high utility.

The posterior uncertainty is the joint probability of data and science objective normalized by the marginal probability of the data, following Bayes theorem:

$$Po(y|\mathbf{x}) = \frac{\int \delta(y - \mathcal{M}(\alpha)) \delta(\mathbf{x} - \mathcal{D}(\alpha)) Pe(\alpha) d\alpha}{\int \delta(\mathbf{x} - \mathcal{D}(\alpha)) Pe(\alpha) d\alpha}. \quad (4)$$

In practice, this division is nearly impracticable because the distribution of simulated data in a hyperdimensional space is extremely sparse. An emulator of the data, which is a functional form for $\mathcal{D}(\alpha)$, is actually needed. An objective quantification for the utility of an observing system is the degree to which the posterior $Po(y|\mathbf{x})$ in equation 3 is narrower than the prior in the scientific objective $Pr_y(y)$ in equation 2. The logarithm of the ratio of their widths is the same as the number of bits according to Shannon information theory.

The quality of a proposed observing system requires an accounting for uncertainty in the data. Measurement uncertainty is mathematically described by the likelihood function $\mathcal{E}(\mathbf{d}|\mathbf{x})$, which represents the probability of obtaining data \mathbf{d} given perfect data \mathbf{x} as it might have been

obtained without instrument noise, time varying calibration drift, or uncertain calibration across observation gaps. Note that missions must provide such a statistical model for the uncertainties. With this description of the noise, the actual a posteriori for the science objective is

$$\text{Po}(y|\mathbf{d}) = \int \mathcal{E}(\mathbf{d}|\mathbf{x}) \text{Po}(y|\mathbf{x}) d\mathbf{x}. \quad (5)$$

By far the most common form for the measurement error likelihood function will be normal distribution. In a COSSE, this would be executed by adding Gaussian random numbers with prescribed standard deviation to the model simulations of the data. If the cause of the noise is imprecision, then independent random numbers are added to each simulated data element. If the cause of the noise is inaccuracy, then a single random number is assigned to a many elements of simulated data. The overall utility and quality of the proposed observing system is the ratio of the widths of the prior distribution $\text{Pr}_y(y)$ and the posterior distribution $\text{Po}(y|\mathbf{d})$. Expanding equation 5 yields

$$\text{Po}(y|\mathbf{d}) = \frac{\iint \delta(y-\mathcal{M}(\alpha)) \delta(\mathbf{x}-\mathcal{D}(\alpha)) \mathcal{E}(\mathbf{d}|\mathbf{x}) \text{Pe}(\alpha) d\alpha d\mathbf{x}}{\iint \delta(\mathbf{x}-\mathcal{D}(\alpha)) \mathcal{E}(\mathbf{d}|\mathbf{x}) \text{Pe}(\alpha) d\alpha d\mathbf{x}}. \quad (6)$$

This is the COSSE equation for observing systems intended to improve predictive skill. Quantification of the error depends strongly on the definition of the observable \mathbf{x} . If it is just the calibrated radiance observations, then only precision and accuracy of the measurements needs to be considered in $\mathcal{E}(\mathbf{d}|\mathbf{x})$. For geophysical variables, retrieval uncertainties will need to be considered. In the case of climate trends, both factors may play an important role depending on the quantified science objective.

In the case of hypothesis testing, two different models produce priors on the data $\text{Pr}_x(\mathbf{x}|M_1)$ and $\text{Pr}_x(\mathbf{x}|M_2)$. The effects of measurement error are determined as for observing systems intended for improving predictive skill:

$$\text{Pr}_d(\mathbf{d}|M_i) = \int \mathcal{E}(\mathbf{d}|\mathbf{x}) \text{Pr}_x(\mathbf{x}|M_i) d\mathbf{x}. \quad (7)$$

If the data \mathbf{d} is more consistent with one distribution $\text{Pr}_d(\mathbf{d}|M_i)$ than others, a strong hypothesis test was performed. High *utility* means the distributions $\text{Pr}_x(\mathbf{x}|M_1)$ and $\text{Pr}_x(\mathbf{x}|M_2)$ do not overlap significantly. High utility and quality mean the distributions $\text{Pr}_d(\mathbf{d}|M_1)$ and $\text{Pr}_d(\mathbf{d}|M_2)$ do not overlap significantly.

Structural error can be found by evaluating the Bayesian evidence function. The evidence E is the integral in the denominator of the COSSE equation:

$$E(\mathbf{d}) = \iint \delta(\mathbf{x} - \mathcal{D}(\alpha)) \mathcal{E}(\mathbf{d}|\mathbf{x}) \text{Pe}(\alpha) d\mathbf{x} d\alpha \quad (8)$$

The evidence is a determination of whether or not all of the data is consistent or inconsistent with what we know about the climate, including our known uncertainties about the climate as determined by the expert prior $\text{Pe}(\alpha)$. If data is collected that is inconsistent with our present knowledge of the climate's workings, it will show up in the evidence as a small number. It is typically not difficult to determine what component or field in the data contains the signature of an inconsistency if the evidence indicates that one exists. It is a useful computation that adds confidence to a prediction for a complex system.

In the context of a COSSE, simulated data is used in the place of actual data in order to evaluate the scientific value of a proposed mission or determine its precision and accuracy requirements. In order to evaluate the power of the evidence function, however, it is clear that a model that is independent of the core model used in the COSSE integral must be used to simulate data \mathbf{d} . In applying such an independent model to probe for structural uncertainties, the COSSE

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can determine how much and what kind of data would be useful for giving confidence to the predictions. If the evidence cannot reveal structural uncertainty, then the model for the data $\mathcal{D}(\alpha)$ must be expanded—new components of the observing program added—to reveal possible structural error. As discussed in §3.2, this is especially important for cases in which the relevant aspects of the core model are considered weak.

11. Appendix B: Centralized vs. decentralized COSSE considerations

There are two major methods that could be used to improve NASA’s COSSE capability. The first would be to provide ROSES specific calls for COSSE studies (decentralized). The second would be to build an in-house NASA modeling capability (analogous to GEOS-5 or the GISS climate model) with a mission to develop, implement, and publish COSSE studies.

Characteristic Grades: 100 = excellent, 90 = very good, 80 = good, 70 = acceptable, 50 = poor

	Centralized	Decentralized
Social: Conflict of Interest & Politics		
Avoiding conflict of interest for obs scientist (assumes observation PI not at COSSE institution)	100	80 (peer review of proposal/results)
Avoiding conflict of interest for COSSE institution (i.e., mission and COSSE institution the same)	50 (wall off)	100 (peer review)
Avoiding political study selections	70 (wall off)	100 (peer review)
Organizational Structure		
Organizational stability (e.g., retain expertise)	100	70
Organizational flexibility (use new approaches)	70	100
Expandability (start small, then grow or reduce)	70	100
Science Quality		
Expertise in models used for COSSEs	80	100
Ability to attract top modeling talent	70	100
Innovation	80	100
Observers/modelers science communication and collaboration effectiveness	70	100
Ability to improve model design/testing	90	100
Ability to improve observation decision making	100	100
Journal publication record	80	100
Programmatic		
Quick turnaround for NASA HQ directed studies	100	60
Cost effectiveness	70	100
Communication of NASA observation logic to science community, Congress, public	100	100
Average Score	81	94

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These considerations suggest that a ROSES program type call for OSSE proposals may lead to the most accepted, effective, and efficient approach to an improved NASA COSSE space mission and field experiment capability. The form of a COSSE program within NASA Earth Sciences should be discussed in the special symposium previously mentioned in §8.1

Note that 100 is just the scaled “best” option, not indicative of perfect results, which are unrealistic using any approach.